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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DG	Distributed Generation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HTD	Holistic Test Description
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
NA	Networking Activities
NCP	National Contact Point
PV	Photovoltaic
PoC	Person of Contact
RDI	Research, Development, and Innovation
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROS	Robot Operating System
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RTS	Real-Time Simulation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TA	Trans-national Access
TF	Task Force
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

ERIGrid 2.0 aims to offer a broad spectrum of advanced services and tools for researchers who are active in smart grids, smart energy systems, and the integration of renewable energies. In particular, the provision of its Research Infrastructures (RIs) and contributing to the integration of Europe's RIs are the major focus of the project. Moreover, the consortium recognises that by establishing new connections and continuing existing collaborations with other relevant projects and initiatives in the smart energy domain are essential for reaching these objectives. Thus, they can be considered as direct contributors to the success of ERIGrid 2.0.

Within ERIGrid 2.0 a set of collaboration and networking activities has been carried out whereas the focus areas of these collaboration activities encompass the full range of research topics within the scope of ERIGrid 2.0. Furthermore, these activities are also geographically varied, targeting projects, networks, and initiatives at national, European, and intercontinental levels. In this report, a summary of the collaboration activities carried out from the period of October 2022 to March 2024 is presented as a complement to the previous releases.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document reports an update of the number of broad collaboration activities that were carried out by ERIGrid 2.0 from 1 October 2022 until 31 March 2024. This is the last release of the reports of project networking and collaboration activities carried out in the project. Likewise, the collaborations holding potential for joint activities shortly are also taken into account. The purpose of this overview is to help the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium assess whether its collaboration with other initiatives is on track and whether its research agenda is reflected in its networking activities. The addressed projects and networks are thematically linked to ERIGrid 2.0, and at least one person is participating in both parties and acting as a Person of Contact (PoC) for collaboration between the parties.

Joint activities between ERIGrid 2.0 and its collaborators are essential to the success of this project. As reflected in the Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019), collaborators are providing feedback to ERIGrid 2.0 activities, stimulating further improvements of the integrated RI. ERIGrid 2.0 in turn will support their activities by sharing methods and experiences on laboratory-based testing and validation of smart grid concepts, as well as offering free access to its state-of-the-art laboratories. Thus, the collaboration and knowledge exchange activities described in this report include webinars, seminars, workshops, national and international conferences, etc. held during the indicated period.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides general details about the background of collaboration activities and outlines the report's purpose and scope. Section 2 gives an overview of projects on European and national levels that ERIGrid 2.0 is collaborating with. Furthermore, in Section 3, an overview of collaborative efforts with networks is presented. The report is concluded in Section 4.

2 Collaborations with Projects

In the first stage of the project, ERIGrid 2.0 identified several relevant European and national projects for cooperation and knowledge exchange. Moreover, these collaborations should be able to provide valuable feedback about project results and contribute to their exploitation. The nature and contents of the collaborations in the currently reported time frame are described in the following sections.

2.1 European Projects

Table 1 outlines the European projects which are collaborating with ERIGrid 2.0. In the following sections, more details are provided about the cooperation with those projects.

Table 1: Overview of European projects with links to ERIGrid 2.0.

Name	Funding	ERIGrid 2.0 Partners Involved	ERIGrid 2.0 PoC	Project PoC
RISEnergy	Horizon Europe	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Thomas Strasser (AIT)
RICH Europe	Horizon Europe	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Andrea Pantarelli (ARPE)
int:net	Horizon Europe	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Antonello Monti, Alberto Dognini (Fraunhofer)
StoRIES	Horizon 2020	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Stefano Passerini (KIT)
PANTERA	Horizon 2020	yes	Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab)	Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab), Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS)
eNeuron	Horizon 2020	yes	Leonard Ramos (DERlab)	Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab)
HYPERRIDE	Horizon 2020	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Thomas Strasser (AIT)
SINERGY	Horizon 2020	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Thomas Strasser (AIT)
RE-EMPOWERED	Horizon 2020	yes	Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)	Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)
JPP Smart Energy Systems	ERA-Net/Horizon 2020	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Michael Hübner (bmk), Ludwig Karg (B.A.U.M.)
ELECTRA	Integrated Projects – Smart Growth/RIF	yes	George Makrides (FOSS)	George Makrides (FOSS)
EDDIE	Erasmus +	yes	Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)	Alexandros Chronis (ICCS-NTUA)
RESili8	ERA-Net/Horizon 2020	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Filip Prössl Andrén (AIT)

2.1.1 RISEnergy

Full Name: Research Infrastructure Services for Renewable Energy (RISEnergy)

Funding Framework: Horizon Europe

Coordinator: Peter Holtappels (KIT)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of StoRIES: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

Project Duration: 1 March 2024 - 31 August 2028

Description: The European Green Deal aims for a zero net greenhouse gas emissions economy by 2050. *RISEnergy*¹, a RI consortium of 69 beneficiaries from 23 countries, fosters innovation in energy technologies. It focuses on improving efficiency, promoting renewables, and offering access to facilities. Its objectives include enhancing research, facilitating transnational access to facilities, engaging stakeholders, and providing high-quality services tailored to academia, industry, and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs).

Collaboration Activities: Having partly similar target audiences, ERIGrid 2.0 and RISEnergy are collaborating on the knowledge exchange and networking related to RIs and the corresponding access provision.

2.1.2 RICH Europe

Full Name: Research Infrastructures Consortium of NCPs in Horizon Europe (RICH Europe)

Funding Framework: Horizon Europe

Coordinator: Andrea Pantarelli (APRE)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of RICH Europe: Andrea Pantarelli (ARPE)

Project Duration: 1 June 2022 - 31 May 2029

Description: The aim of *RICH Europe*² is to improve and support the professionalisation and harmonisation of RI National Contact Points (NCPs) services across Europe and to contribute to the consolidation of the European research infrastructure ecosystem.

Collaboration Activities: Having similar target audiences, ERIGrid 2.0 and RICH Europe collaborated on knowledge exchange and networking related to RIs and the corresponding access provision. On 23 November 2022, ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator Thomas Strasser (AIT) participated in the “*First Webinar of RICH Europe on Transnational and Virtual access opportunities (TA/VA)*” organised by RICH Europe and held a presentation on “*The ERIGrid 2.0 RI Access Opportunities*”. The presentation aimed to promote both Trans-national Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) opportunities offered by ERIGrid 2.0. Moreover, RICH Europe is sharing all ERIGrid 2.0 lab access (i.e., TA) calls with its community.

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131793>

²<https://rich-europe.eu/>

2.1.3 int:net

Full Name: Interoperability Network for the Energy Transition (int:net)

Funding Framework: Horizon Europe

Coordinator: Antonello Monti (Fraunhofer)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of int:net: Antonello Monti, Alberto Dognini (Fraunhofer)

Project Duration: 1 May 2022 - 30 April 2025

Description: *int:net*³ brings together all stakeholders relevant to the European energy sector to jointly work on developing, testing, and deploying interoperable energy solutions and services. This project will also push for improved cooperation between energy services to ensure synchronisation between providers.

Collaboration Activities: Having similar target audiences, ERIGrid 2.0 and int:net collaborated on knowledge exchange and networking related to validation facilities with a focus on interoperability testing.

2.1.4 StoRIES

Full Name: Storage Research Infrastructure Eco-System (StoRIES)

Funding Framework: Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Stefano Passerini, Myriam E. Gil Bardaji (KIT)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of StoRIES: Yannick Wimmer (AIT)

Project Duration: 1 November 2021 - 31 October 2025

Description: *StoRIES*⁴ promotes a European ecosystem of industry and research organisations to develop innovative concepts and competitive and less costly energy storage technologies. The consortium consists of members of the European Energy Research Alliance and the European Association for Storage of Energy. By providing access to first-rate RIs and services, the project will speed up the advancement of knowledge and technology in the field of energy storage. One of its technological goals is to optimise hybrid energy systems.

Collaboration Activities: Having similar target audiences, ERIGrid 2.0 and StoRIES collaborated on knowledge exchange and networking related to RIs and the corresponding access provision. During the *EES-UETP Workshop on Advanced Laboratory System Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems* held on the 8-10 May 2023 at TU Dortmund (Germany), Kai Heussen (DTU) conducted a presentation on “*System Testing for Multi-Domain Energy Systems*” in which, among other topics, the outcomes from the collaboration of ERIGrid 2.0, SIRFN project and DTU were described. Further, the StoRIES project’s TA calls are promoted as well.

³<https://intnet-project.eu/>

⁴<https://www.storiesproject.eu/>

2.1.5 PANTERA

Full Name: Pan European Technology Energy Research Approach (PANTERA)

Funding Framework: Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab)

PoC on Behalf of PANTERA: Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab), Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS)

Project Duration: 1 September 2019 - 30 June 2023

Description: *PANTERA*⁵ set up a European forum composed of Research & Innovation stakeholders active in the fields of smart grids, storage and local energy systems, including policy-makers, standardisation bodies and experts in both research and academia representing the European Union (EU) energy system. The project created the corresponding multi-functional collaborative platform EIRIE, which serves as a reference operational point to unify European activities, to incentivise further investments in smart grids and to support access to exploitable results.

Collaboration Activities: Having similar target audiences, ERIGrid 2.0 and PANTERA collaborated for knowledge exchange and networking. Furthermore, PANTERA's EIRIE platform presented lab access and virtual services offered by ERIGrid 2.0. During the final event of the EIRIE Platform, held on 9 July 2023, EIRIE's regional research collaboration was discussed. Under Regional Desk 2, TU Sofia, the responsible partner, covered a call titled "*Regional research collaboration*". The sub-topic was "*Services offered to the R&I community of available R&I infrastructure*". This offered collaborative options such as the TA provided by the ERIGrid 2.0 project which enables collaborative access to the leading laboratories of Europe is highly supportive and efficient for the R&I stakeholders.

2.1.6 eNeuron

Full Name: greEN Energy hUbs for local integRated energy cOmmunities optimization (eNeuron)

Funding Framework: Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Maria Valenti (ENEA)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Leonard Ramos (DERlab)

PoC on Behalf of eNeuron: Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab)

Project Duration: 1 November 2020 - 31 October 2024

Description: *eNeuron*⁶ will set out a practical and evidence-based framework for optimising the design and operation of local energy communities acting as energy hubs. It will draw on pioneering software and hardware solutions and develop new use cases so that local energy communities can rise to the challenge of widespread roll-out.

Collaboration Activities: With the topic of multi-energy being in the scope of research both for eNeuron and ERIGrid 2.0, some common topics are found between both projects (e.g., on use

⁵<https://pantera-platform.eu/>

⁶<https://eneuron.eu/>

cases and testing requirements and methodologies). The ERIGRID 2.0 consortium was invited to participate in an online workshop on “*Integrated local (multi-carrier) energy communities: economic aspects of energy communities - Business models and use cases*” held on 20 March 2024 as part of knowledge transfer and project collaboration activities.

2.1.7 HYPERRIDE

Full Name: HYbrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency via Integration of DC Equipment (HYPERRIDE)

Funding Framework: Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Gerhard Jambrich (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGRID 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

Poc on Behalf of HYPERRIDE: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

Project Duration: 1 October 2020 - 31 March 2025

Description: *HYPERRIDE*⁷ will contribute to the field implementation of Direct Current (DC) and hybrid Alternating Current (AC)/DC grids by identifying and providing solutions to overcome barriers for a successful roll-out of new infrastructure concepts throughout Europe. Under the coordination of AIT, 10 consortium partners from 6 European countries develop grid planning and operation guidelines and adapt available sizing tools for DC. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of enabling technologies will be raised focused on Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) breakers, sensors and DC measurement units to provide field-ready devices for grid automation and protection. During the project’s lifetime, automation algorithms will be created, validated and transferred to demo sites. This involves concepts and solutions for cyber-security and fault mitigation to avoid cascading effects. Pilot sites are implemented in Aachen (Germany), Lausanne (Switzerland), and Terni (Italy) to showcase the above-mentioned technologies. Finally, the solutions are evaluated, focusing especially on the benefits of the integration potential of renewables. Furthermore, business models will be created for products, services and applications.

Collaboration Activities: Concerning the HYPERRIDE efforts and ambition of developing grid automation and protection concepts (cyber-security concepts), there are numerous interfaces and common research topics with ERIGRID 2.0. The two projects keep common ground when it comes to educational activities (together with EPFL University) and the validation of results. The ERIGRID 2.0 and HYPERRIDE projects had a joint booth at *CIREN 2023: International Conference & Exhibition on Electricity Distribution* held in Rome (Italy) from 12-15 June 2023. This conference stands for the Leading Forum where the electricity distribution community meets, and holds the major International Electricity Conference and Exhibition every two years in different venues of Europe with a worldwide perspective and participation. During the exhibition, both ERIGRID 2.0 and HYPERRIDE projects showcased the latest project results from their technical activities.

2.1.8 SINERGY

Full Name: Capacity building in Smart and Innovative eENERGY management (SINERGY)

⁷<https://hyperride.eu/>

Funding Framework: Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Nikola Tomašević, Valentina Janev (IMP)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

Poc on Behalf of SINERGY: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

Project Duration: 1 January 2021 - 31 December 2023

Description: *SINERGY*⁸ has the primary objective to strengthen the research capacity and to further unlock the innovation potential of the Institute Mihajlo Pupin (IMP), transforming it into a regional Centre of Excellence in smart energy management. Once established, as a novel regional excellence centre, IMP will promote the added value of smart energy management technologies, coordinate research efforts and unite scarce research resources in this field in the Southeast European region. Further, it encourages communication with leading external EU parties, aiming at full integration into the European Research Area (ERA). In this way, IMP will be capable of further disseminating the project outcomes (strategies, policies, training courses, webinars, etc.) and supporting companies and institutions (both research and industrial) in the region to strengthen their EU competitiveness. To reach *SINERGY*'s ambitious objectives, a strategic partnership and transfer of multidisciplinary "know-how" from leading EU research institutions, and beyond, will play a central role in gaining and exchanging the related competencies needed for the development of high-impact innovative energy management solutions suitable for efficient and reliable energy networks of the future.

Collaboration Activities: There are several common research questions between ERIGrid 2.0 and *SINERGY*, especially in the areas of validating smart energy systems and corresponding educational activities. From 19 to 22 February 2024, the projects ERIGrid 2.0, *SINERGY*, and RESili8 organised an online training series related to *digitalisation of smart energy systems*. A total of four online lectures were held, with presenters from the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology in Vienna (Austria) and Institute Mihajlo Pupin (IMP), in Belgrade (Serbia). ERIGrid 2.0 participated in two out of four lectures held, in which the outcomes of the project served as a reference. One lecture elaborated on the topic "*Modelling and simulation of integrated energy systems*" and was presented by Edmund Widl (AIT), while the other lecture focused on "*Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems*" and was presented by ERIGrid 2.0 Coordinator Thomas Strasser (AIT) in collaboration with Filip Pröbstl Andrén (AIT).

2.1.9 RE-EMPOWERED

Full Name: Renewable Energy EMPOWERing European and InDian communities (RE-EMPOWERED)

Funding Framework: Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Nikos Hatziaargyriou (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of RE-EMPOWERED: Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)

Project Duration: 1 July 2021 - 31 December 2024

Description: *RE-EMPOWERED*⁹ aims to develop a set of solutions (ecoToolset) for efficient, decarbonised and RES-intensive multi-energy islanded/isolated communities and microgrids.

⁸<https://project-sinergy.org/>

⁹<https://reempowered-h2020.com/>

The tools will facilitate energy planning, energy management and optimal operation of the local energy systems, demand side management and demand response capabilities, communication of the various tools, implementation of control algorithms through smart converters, monitoring of the quality of the surrounding environment, etc. Special focus will be given to exploiting synergies among energy vectors, increasing demand flexibility through customer engagement using digitalisation that will foster an active energy community via sustainable business plans and investments. The solutions of the toolset will be tailored to the specific needs of four pilot cases in the EU and India but will aim at a wide target group for replication and exploitation in both the developed and developing world.

Collaboration Activities: In the frame of RE-EMPOWERED, the Holistic Test Description (HTD) template developed and expanded in ERIGrid 2.0 was used to set and describe the test scenarios for the stability studies for the demo sites. Thus, ERIGrid 2.0 gained more exposure in activities within RE-EMPOWERED EU-India Project. On 16 February 2023, ICCS (in representation of the ERIGrid 2.0 project) co-organised a workshop with the RE-EMPOWERED project and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) PELs Society Joint Chapter Kolkata/Bhubaneswar, IEEE Bhubaneswar subsection in IIT BBS in India. Within the framework of this workshop, ICCS presented the ERIGrid 2.0 project scope and major developments, as well as the TA and VA possibilities, disseminating the opportunities among students from India.

2.1.10 JPP Smart Energy Systems

Full Name: ERA-Net Digitalisation of Energy Systems and Networks (JPP Smart Energy Systems)

Funding Framework: ERA-Net/Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Michael Hübner (bmk)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of JPP Smart Energy Systems: Michael Hübner (bmk), Ludwig Karg (B.A.U.M.)

Project Duration: 1 December 2020 - 30 November 2025

Description: *JPP Smart Energy Systems*¹⁰ offers a sustainable, reliable, and efficient management structure for multilateral joint programming. The Steering Board and Management Board provide the framework for joint planning, decision-making, and collaborative implementation of joint calls and joint activities. The Coordination supports the partners in strategy, decision-making and governance, cooperation of programs and partners, communication and dissemination, organisation of joint calls, and contractual and financial management. Beyond that, the JPP Smart Energy Systems is well coordinated with the European SET-Plan Action 4 initiatives.

Collaboration Activities: ERIGrid 2.0 and the JPP Smart Energy Systems have set up a formal cooperation where ERIGrid 2.0 is an associated partner and also a partner in the living labs and testbeds network. Both projects/initiatives can potentially exchange and share knowledge related to the validation of smart energy systems, as well as to related testing facilities and approaches. During the last two years ERIGrid 2.0 coordinator contributed with some talks and inputs/feedback to the JPP Smart Energy Systems community, especially during the annual conferences.

¹⁰<https://www.eranet-smartenergysystems.eu/>

2.1.11 ELECTRA

Full Name: Modernising the distribution grid for enabling high penetration of photovoltaic electricity through advanced data analytic operational observability and management (ELECTRA)

Funding Framework: Integrated Projects – Smart Growth/RIF

Coordinator: George Makrides (FOSS)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: George Makrides (FOSS)

Poc on Behalf of GIFT: George Makrides (FOSS)

Project Duration: 1 June 2020 – 30 June 2023

Description: *ELECTRA*¹¹ aimed to fuse extensive interdisciplinary research in the field of grid integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and targeted the major challenges and barriers to boost the integration of RES, by covering the whole research and innovation spectrum of enabling dynamic, automated and cost-effective management of smart distribution grids.

Essentially, the main aim of ELECTRA was to pave the way for increased penetration of Distributed Generation (DG) systems (predominantly solar Photovoltaic (PV) systems), to be integrated and optimally managed at the distribution grid level. Since the strong growth and uptake of the photovoltaic sector (future dominant renewable technology at the distribution system) is also associated with the potential of the grid to accommodate the variability of DG, a key factor that will boost the further increase and uptake of the technology is to enable the efficient and reliable operation of future distribution systems with high DG shares. This can only be achieved by modernising the distribution grid for real-time predictive observability and automated control with the use of advanced data analytics that leverages machine learning principles. An important aspect of this project was also the development of an adaptive multi-service distribution management architecture (end-solution) that provided the required bi-directional electricity flow control and flexibility in distribution grids with high RES shares.

Collaboration Activities: ELECTRA and ERIGrid 2.0 are sharing common research points that were used for collaboration. Both projects are engaged with advanced controls of PV and storage systems, centralised control for smart grids and full Distributed Energy Resources (DER) digitalisation for real-time controls. During the *EES-UETP Workshop on Advanced Laboratory System Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems* held on the 8-10 May 2023 in TU Dortmund (Germany), in which ERIGrid 2.0, SIRFN project and DTU collaborated, the case study on *peer-to-peer frequency control* developed under ELECTRA project was part of the presentation on “*System Testing for Multi-Domain Energy Systems*” conducted by Kai Heussen (DTU).

2.1.12 EDDIE

Full Name: EDucation for Digitalisation of Energy (EDDIE)

Funding Framework: Erasmus +

Coordinator: Fernando de Cuadra García and Miguel Ángel Sánchez Fornié (Comillas Universidad Pontificia)

¹¹<https://fosscy.eu/projects/electra/>

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of EDDIE: Alexandros Chronis (ICCS-NTUA)

Project Duration: 1 January 2020 - 31 December 2023

Description: *EDDIE*¹² aims to develop a Blueprint Strategy for the Digitalisation of the Energy value chain (BSDE). It will be based on the sustainable cooperation between key industry stakeholders, education and training providers, social partners and public authorities. The BSDE is an industry-driven strategy that will meet and anticipate the skills demands for the sustainable growth and digitalisation of the European Energy sector. This new strategic approach will reinforce the competitiveness of the European Energy Sector efficiently and innovatively by creating a highly skilled workforce.

Collaboration Activities: There were several common topics between the projects, especially in the area of coping with the skill demands for the energy sector and energy transition, as well as the appropriate educational activities and methods to facilitate the training of the targeted audience. From 27 to 29 March 2023, EDDIE, ERIGrid 2.0 and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems co-organised a tutorial session on *Emerging skill needs and training tools for professionals and researchers in the field of smart energy systems* under the framework of the *2nd International workshop on Open Source Modelling and Simulation of Energy Systems OSMSES 2023*, held in Aachen (Germany). Among others, the tutorial showcased the work of both ERIGrid 2.0 and EDDIE projects.

Furthermore, from 21 to 22 April 2023 the *NSF Joint US European Workshop: Flexible Electric Grid Critical Infrastructure for Resilient Society* was held. Prof. Nikos Hatziaargyriou moderated the first topic on *The decision and control fundamentals for improved grid reliability and resilience*, whereas Alexandros Chronis (ICCS-NTUA) presented insights and open questions produced by the ongoing work of EDDIE, the ERIGrid 2.0 and APEX (Smart Management Hub of Renewable Energy Sources and Energy Efficiency) projects during the discussion on the topic *The education and training fundamentals for the realisation and support of a resilient society*.

Lastly, on 18 July 2023, during the 2023 *IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting* held in Orlando (USA), APEX, EDDIE and ERIGrid 2.0 projects collaborated in a knowledge exchange activity. The idea was to disseminate innovative teaching methods and material in modern power and energy systems and promote advanced technical tools for education and training. Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA) highlighted the key takeaways from the hands-on experiences of using advanced technical tools (Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), virtual and remote labs) gained in the context of ERIGrid 2.0.

2.1.13 RESili8

Full Name: Resilience for Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (RESili8)

Funding Framework: ERA-Net/Horizon 2020

Coordinator: Filip Pröbstl Andrén (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of RESili8: Filip Pröbstl Andrén (AIT)

¹²<https://www.eddie-erasmus.eu/>

Project Duration: 1 May 2022 - 30 April 2025

Description: RESili8¹³ develops a novel resilience solution package for cyber-physical energy systems, introducing new methods and tools for resilient planning, implementation, and operation of energy systems. The project has three main goals:

- Resilience Engineering Support: RESili8 will develop a toolkit that will support system operators to optimally design, plan, and evaluate resilient cyber-physical energy systems.
- Implementing Resilient Applications: RESili8 will support stakeholders to exhaustively and rapidly test and refine their applications at the system level before deployment.
- Resilience Runtime Support: RESili8 will develop a resilience runtime support system that can suggest—and execute—actions to recover a system back to a normal state.

Collaboration Activities: As mentioned in Section 2.1.8, ERIGrid 2.0, together with SINERGY and RESili8 projects, organised an online training series related to *digitalisation of smart energy systems* from 19 to 22 February 2024. ERIGrid 2.0 participated in two lectures held, in which the outcomes of the project served as reference. The topics “*Modelling and simulation of integrated energy systems*” and “*Designing and Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems*” were the focus of the discussion.

2.2 National Projects

ERIGrid 2.0 collaborated in the past with national projects such as PoSyCo, Project 2.2 and Project 2.3, which ended in 2021. These activities were already reported in past releases of this deliverable (*D-NA2.2a Progress Report of Project Networking and Collaboration Activities, 2021*; *D-NA2.2b Progress Report of Project Networking and Collaboration Activities, 2023*). Apart from these projects, Table 2 provides an overview of other projects at the national level that cooperated with ERIGrid 2.0 in the reported period.

Table 2: Overview of national projects with links to ERIGrid 2.0.

Name	Funding	ERIGrid 2.0 Partners Involved	ERIGrid 2.0 PoC	Project PoC
PowerTeams	FFG (Austria)	yes	Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Filip Prössl Andrén (AIT)
NFDI4Energy	DFG (Germany)	yes	Oliver Werth (OFFIS)	Oliver Werth (OFFIS)
APEX	EL.ID.E.K. (Greece)	yes	Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)	Alexandros Chronis (ICCS-NTUA)

In the following sections, further details on the cooperation with these projects are provided.

2.2.1 PowerTeams

Full Name: Collaborative engineering of smart grid applications (PowerTeams)

Funding Framework: Austrian National Energy Research Programme (7th Call 2021)

Coordinator: Christof Brandauer (SRFG)

¹³<https://www.resili8-project.eu/>

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of PowerTeams: Filip Pröbstl Andrén (AIT)

Project Duration: 1 April 2022 - 31 March 2025

Description: *PowerTeams*¹⁴ addresses the concept of a model-based, service-oriented, and cooperative development and validation platform for smart grid applications to cope with future requirements. The goal is to develop an architecture of an interoperable, distributed, and service-oriented ecosystem that offers modular services to collaborative development teams for automation-supported engineering over the entire application lifecycle. This platform enables the management of engineering data, which is necessary for continuous, transparent and interoperable digitisation of the energy system. The concept will be validated using a proof-of-concept implementation and selected use cases.

Collaboration Activities: ERIGrid 2.0 results related to validation and testing (especially virtual services) provide essential inputs that can be integrated into the PowerTeams platform. Furthermore, experiences and improvement suggestions are feedback from PowerTeams to ERIGrid 2.0.

2.2.2 NFDI4Energy

Full Name: National Research Data Infrastructure for Interdisciplinary Energy System Research (NFDI4Energy)

Funding Framework: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)

Coordinator: Astrid Nieße (Carl von Ossietzky University Oldenburg)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Oliver Werth (OFFIS)

PoC on Behalf of NFDI4Energy: Oliver Werth (OFFIS)

Project Duration: 1 March 2023 - 29 February 2028

Description: *NFDI4Energy*¹⁵ covers the whole research and transfer cycle of projects in energy system research including: identifying relevant competencies for a project, defining relevant scenarios and experimental setup, integrating models and data, coupling tools and laboratories, extracting results, facilitating public consultation, and identifying research challenges for follow-up activities. Thus, the project key objectives stand for:

- Establishing common research community services for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) data, models, and processes.
- Allowing traceability, reproducibility, and transparency of results for the scientific community as well as for society, improving the overall FAIR.
- Enable and motivate the involvement of society for the identification and solution of relevant research questions.
- Promoting better collaboration and knowledge transfer between scientific research institutes and business partners via FAIR research data management.
- Simplifying identification, integration, and coordination of simulation-based models.

¹⁴<https://www.salzburgresearch.at/en/projekt/powerteams/>

¹⁵<https://nfdi4energy.uol.de/>

- Integrating the provided services for energy system research within the wider NFDI ecosystem to improve cross-domain collaboration.

Therefore, to fulfil these objectives, the NFDI4Energy project concentrates on five key services to provide non-discriminatory access to digital research objects: (i) Competence to help to navigate the interdisciplinary research field, (ii) Best Practices to get information about the successful conduct of research including research data management, (iii) Registry to find suitable data and software, (iv) Simulation to couple existing simulations and, therefore, reuse of software artefacts, and (v) Transparency to involve more stakeholders at all research stages.

Collaboration Activities: ERIGrid 2.0 results provide essential contents related to its overall structure and requirements that can be integrated and (re-used) in the NFDI4Energy platform. The first NFDI4Energy conference was held between 16 and 21 February 2024 in Hannover (Germany). During this conference, experiences from the ERIGrid 2.0 project were exchanged to conceptualise the requirements for the NFDI4Energy workshop. Furthermore, experiences and improvement suggestions are reported back from NFDI4Energy to ERIGrid 2.0 and vice versa to foster knowledge exchange.

2.2.3 APEX

Full Name: APEX - Smart Management Hub of Renewable Energy Sources and Energy Efficiency (by its translation into English)

Funding Framework: Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (EL.ID.E.K. by its abbreviation in English)

Coordinator: Nikolaos Chatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of APEX: Alexandros Chronis (ICCS-NTUA)

Project Duration: 1 July 2021 - 30 November 2023

Description: APEX¹⁶ aimed to transfer scientific knowledge and innovation to secondary education regarding modern electrical energy systems, renewable sources, energy saving and smart grids. A focus was set on the development of environmental awareness based on scientific evidence and published data. Further emphasis was placed on studying the educational methodologies used and on the familiarisation with the curricula of the classes targeted (VETs, Senior high school, Junior high school). Then the content of the three educational visits to the hubs was formulated, which provided the opportunity for a broad familiarisation with the topic of the energy transition (Introductory visit comprising of three modules) and for a deeper understanding of the individual modules of “Energy saving” and “RES and smart grids” (two targeted visits, one for each topic). In parallel, the design of the two hubs (central hub in Sivitanidio school and remote hub in Mytilene school) was performed, which involved selecting the installation sites, sizing the equipment and market research. The physical hubs were supported by online tools that were made available on the website of the project.

Collaboration Activities: As mentioned in Subsection 2.1.11, APEX and ERIGrid 2.0 (together with EDDIE) collaborated during the *NSF Joint US European Workshop: Flexible Electric Grid Critical Infrastructure for Resilient Society* by addressing insights and open questions produced by the ongoing work of both projects ERIGrid 2.0 and discussing on education

¹⁶<https://apex.edu.gr/>

and training fundamentals for the realisation and resiliency enhancement of society. Likewise, both projects collaborated during the 2023 *IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting* through the dissemination of innovative teaching methods and material in modern energy systems and the promotion of advanced technical tools for education and training.

3 Collaborations with Initiatives

The cooperation and information exchange on a broader scale is also an important point for disseminating and exploiting potential project results as well as gathering feedback about them. Therefore, ERIGrid 2.0 already identified several such initiatives considered to be worth collaborating. Table 3 outlines those networks, platforms, and initiatives where ERIGrid 2.0 has already set up connections or is planning to do so soon.

Table 3: Overview of networks, platforms, and initiatives with links to ERIGrid 2.0.

Name	Type	ERIGrid 2.0 Partners Involved	ERIGrid 2.0 PoC	Network PoC
European Initiatives				
EERA JP Smart Grids	Network (European)	yes	Evangelos Rikos (CRES), Kari Mäki (VTT), and others	Luciano Martini (RSE), Evangelos Rikos (CRES), and others
BRIDGE Energy Communities Task Force	Network (European)	yes	Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)	Leen Peeters (ThInk-E), Ludwig Karg (Baum Group)
ETIP SNET	Technology & Innovation Platform (European)	yes	Nikos Hatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA), Kari Mäki (VTT), Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS), Antonello Monti (RWTH)	Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS), Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab), Antonello Monti (RWTH)
National Initiatives				
Smart Otaniemi	Network (national)	yes	Kari Mäki (VTT)	Kari Mäki (VTT)
ENET-RTLlab	Network (European)	yes	Antonio de Paola (JRC)	Andrea Mazza (PoliTO)
International Initiatives				
IEA ISGAN/SIRFN	Network (international)	yes	Mihai Calin (AIT), Kari Mäki (VTT)	Ron Brandl (DERlab)
Mission Innovation IC#1 Smart Grids	Network (international)	yes	Enea Bionda (RSE), Kari Mäki (VTT)	Mattia Cabiati (RSE)
DERlab	Network (international)	yes	Leonard Ramos (DERlab), Greta Meshi (DERlab), Thomas Strasser (AIT)	Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab), Roland Bründlinger (AIT), Graeme Burt (UoS)
IEEE PES Teaching Task Force	Task Force (international)	yes	Panos Kotsampopoulos, Nikos Hatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA), and others	Panos Kotsampopoulos, Nikos Hatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA)
IEEE WG P2004	Working Group (international)	yes	Georg Lauss (AIT), Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA), Antonello Monti (RWTH), Thomas Strasser (AIT), and others	Michael Steurer (FSU), Georg Lauss (AIT)
IEEE PES EICC Task Force	Task Force (international)	yes	Graeme Burt (UoS)	Graeme Burt (UoS)

In the following sections, more details about the cooperation with those initiatives are provided.

3.1 European Initiatives

3.1.1 EERA JP Smart Grids

Full Name: European Energy Research Alliance Joint Programme (EERA JP) Smart Grids

Type: European Network

Coordinator: Luciano Martini (RSE)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Evangelos Rikos (CRES), Kari Mäki (VTT), and others

PoC on behalf of EERA JP SG: Luciano Martini (RSE), Evangelos Rikos (CRES), and others

Description: *EERA JP SG*¹⁷ by means of using an extended cross-disciplinary cooperation involving many research and development participants with different and complementary expertise and facilities, aims at addressing, in a medium to long term research perspective, one of the most critical areas directly relating to the effective acceleration of smart grid deployment: smart grids technology, its application and integration.

Collaboration Activities: Through the link with the EERA JP SG the specific collaboration opportunities with ERIGrid 2.0 included:

- Regular information transfer from the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium on the EERA/EU-related activities, publications, etc.
- Promotion of TA and VA opportunities through the EERA JP SG activities which engage a substantial number of European and international stakeholders.
- As with its predecessor project, there will be an opportunity for external users related to EERA to access the ERIGrid 2.0 facilities, physically or remotely, and benefit from the harmonised testing procedures on the topics that ERIGrid 2.0 covers.
- EERA JP SG will get insights from ERIGrid 2.0 testing methodology developments and the results of investigations about RI needs.
- Potential joint workshops/events.

3.1.2 ETIP SNET

Full Name: European Technology and Innovation Platform Smart Networks for Energy Transition (ETIP SNET)

Type: European Network

Coordinator: Secretariat: Zabala Innovation Consulting (Spain)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Nikos Hatzigargyriou (ICCS-NTUA), Kari Mäki (VTT), Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS), Antonello Monti (RWTH)

¹⁷<https://www.eera-set.eu/component/projects/projects.html?id=53>

PoC on behalf of ETIP SNET: Venizelos Efthymiou (FOSS), Diana Strauss-Mincu (DERlab), Antonello Monti (RWTH)

Description: The *ETIP SNET*¹⁸ role is to guide Research, Development, and Innovation (RDI) to support Europe's energy transition. More specifically, its mission is to set out a vision for RDI for Smart Networks for Energy Transition and engage stakeholders in this vision, prepare and update the Strategic Research and Innovation Roadmap, report on the implementation of RDI activities at European, national/regional and industrial levels.

It provides input to the SET Plan action 4 which addresses the technical challenges raised by the transformation of the energy system, it identifies innovation barriers, notably related to regulation and financing, it develops enhanced knowledge-sharing mechanisms that help bring RDI results to deployment and prepare consolidated stakeholder views on Research and Innovation to European Energy Policy initiatives.

The work is organised through six Working Groups (WGs):

- WG1 Reliable, economic and efficient smart grid system,
- WG2 Storage technologies and sector interfaces,
- WG3 Flexible generation,
- WG4 Digitalisation of the electricity system and customer participation,
- WG5 Innovation implementation in the business environment, and
- WG6 National stakeholders coordination group.

Collaboration Activities: Through the involvement of ERIGrid 2.0 partners DERlab and FOSS in ETIP SNET WG5, there is a continuous process of information sharing about lab access opportunities in ERIGrid 2.0. Under the framework of *2023 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)* held on 1 October 2023 in Honolulu (Hawaii), ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator Thomas Strasser (AIT) disseminated the vision of smart energy networks developed by ETIP SNET during his presentation.

3.1.3 BRIDGE Energy Communities Task Force

Full Name: BRIDGE Task Force on Energy Communities

Type: European Network

Coordinator: Leen Peeters (Th!nk-E), Ludwig Karg (Baum Group)

Support Leader: Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on behalf of BRIDGE Task Force: Leen Peeters (Th!nk-E), Ludwig Karg (Baum Group)

Description: *BRIDGE Task Force on Energy Communities*¹⁹ was established following BRIDGE General Assembly of 2019 to look into existing and upcoming frameworks in various EU countries and to find how the development could be further facilitated.

¹⁸<https://www.etip-snet.eu/>

¹⁹https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-06/bridge_tf_energy_communities_report_2020-2021_0.pdf

The Task Force (TF) has been in charge of preparing reports and formulating recommendations for the European Commission (EC) on the replicability, upscaling, and the need for support, as well as on informing about further research and demonstration needs.

Collaboration Activities: The TF aims to provide an overview of the existing legal developments regarding energy communities in the EU and provide recommendations, highlighting the existing experience of energy communities between countries and specifying the principles of autonomy, effective control, locality, etc. Thus, as in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0 the focus is placed also on energy communities and active engagement of prosumers, a channel of communication with the TF leads to mutual knowledge exchange possibilities.

3.2 National Initiatives

3.2.1 Smart Otaniemi

Full Name: Smart Otaniemi Innovation Ecosystem

Type: National Network

Coordinator: Ismo Heimonen (VTT)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Kari Mäki (VTT)

PoC on behalf of Smart Otaniemi: Kari Mäki (VTT)

Description: *Smart Otaniemi*²⁰ is an innovation ecosystem connecting experts, organisations, technologies and pilot projects bringing together building blocks of a smart future. The aim is to renew the way research and development is done and push the boundaries of new energy technology with Finnish hi-tech excellence. The focus areas are:

- Local flexibility,
- Building level intelligence,
- Smart mobility, and
- Platforms, connectivity and enabling technologies.

Collaboration Activities: A collaboration of Smart Otaniemi is established through the involvement of ERIGrid 2.0 partner VTT on knowledge sharing and piloting via the TA programme of ERIGrid 2.0. During EES-UETP Workshop on *Advanced Laboratory System Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems*, held from 8 to 10 May 2023 in Dortmund (Germany), ERIGrid 2.0 project partner Petra Raussi (VTT) conducted a presentation on “*Wireless 5G for Smart Grid Protection Communication*” in which the 5G network infrastructure available in Espoo’s Otaniemi Campus (Finland) was described as part of the collaboration activities with this network.

3.2.2 ENET-RTLab

Full Name: EnSiEL National Energy Transition Real-Time Lab

Type: National network of laboratories

²⁰<https://smartotaniemi.fi/>

Coordinator: Ettore Bompard (PoliTO)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Antonio De Paola (JRC)

PoC on behalf of ENET-RTLab: Andrea Mazza (PoliTO)

Description: The *EnSiEL National Energy Transition Real-Time Lab* (ENET-RTlab)²¹ is a network of interconnected Italian laboratories for the realization of geographically-distributed real-time simulations. The ENET-RTlab is coordinated by the Energia e Sistemi Elettrici (Ensiel) consortium, which brings together different Italian universities operating in the areas of digital simulations and power systems. ENET-RTLab aims at fostering collaboration and the pooling of expertise and resources between different research institutions, with the final objective of developing and testing new technologies for the energy transition. In particular, the utilisation of geographically distributed real-time simulations enables the sharing of hardware and software resources of multiple research institutions, with more efficient utilisation of the available computational power and opening up the possibility for other research partners to access and utilise costly and powerful equipment.

Collaboration Activities: ENET-RTLab collaborated with ERIGrid 2.0 partners, represented by Antonello Monti (RWTH Aachen) and Thomas Strasser (AIT), in a joint RTDS demonstration (multi-site co-simulation) held during the JRC seminar on *Supporting a global energy transition: from local energy communities to global simulation networks* held from 9 to 10 November 2022. Additionally, during this workshop, the ERIGrid 2.0 project scope, objectives, and opportunities were presented.

3.3 International Initiatives

3.3.1 IEA ISGAN/SIRFN

Full Name: International Smart Grid Action Network (IEA ISGAN) / Smart Grid International Research Facility Network (SIRFN)

Type: International network

Coordinator: Russel Conkling (DOE)

PoC on behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Mihai Calin (AIT), Kari Mäki (VTT), Mazher Syed (UoS)

PoC on behalf of SIRFN: Ron Brandl (DERlab)

Description: *SIRFN*²² gives participating countries the ability to evaluate pre-competitive technologies and system approaches in a wide range of smart grid implementation use cases and geographies using common testing procedures. Research test-bed facilities will be selected based on their complementary capabilities to conduct specialised, controlled laboratory evaluations of integrated smart grid technologies including cyber-security, plug-in hybrid integration, load management, automated metering infrastructure, protection, network sensing, energy management, renewable energy integration and similar applications.

In this way, research within each individual member country will derive the value of the unique capabilities and environments of the other partner nations. Data from these tests will be made available to all SIRFN participants to accelerate the development of smart grid technologies and systems, and enabling policies.

²¹<https://www.linkedin.com/company/enet-rt-lab/>

²²https://www.iea-isgan.org/our-work3/wg_5/

Collaboration Activities: ISGAN/SIRFN and ERIGrid 2.0 collaborated together through a knowledge transfer activity under the framework of EES-UETP Workshop on *Advanced Laboratory System Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems* held on 10 May 2023 in Dortmund (Germany). In this workshop, ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator Thomas Strasser (AIT) and Deputy Coordinator Mihai Calin (AIT) presented “*Challenges and Learnings from Advanced Testing Systems in H2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project*”. SIRFN’s Microgrid Testing and DER Certification Testbeds, its functionality, as well as test protocols and other aspects were described in this presentation.

3.3.2 Mission Innovation IC#1 Smart Grids

Full Name: Mission Innovation Challenge IC#1: Smart Grids

Type: International network

Coordinator: Luciano Martini (RSE), Yibo Wang (CAS), JBV Reddy (DST)

PoC on behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Enea Bionda (RSE), Kari Mäki (VTT)

PoC on behalf of Mission Innovation: Mattia Cabiati (RSE)

Description: *Mission Innovation Challenge IC#1 on Smart Grids*²³ aims to accelerate the development and demonstration of smart grid technologies in a variety of grid applications, including demonstrating the robust, efficient, and reliable operation of regional grids and distribution grids as well as microgrids in diverse geographic conditions, to facilitate the cost-effective uptake of renewable energy. Generally, Mission Innovation (MI) Innovation Challenges (IC) are global calls to action aimed at catalysing global research efforts in areas that could provide significant benefits in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, increasing energy security, and creating new opportunities for clean economic growth.

Collaboration Activities: Within the IC#1 on Smart Grids Italy proposed and coordinated the development of the Smart Grid Innovation Accelerator (SGIA) platform²⁴. SGIA is a cloud-based semantic platform for sharing information regarding the smart grid and, on a more general level, the energy sector. The platform offers an advanced search experience on a database of key documents globally selected and shared by international experts from MI member countries. ERIGrid 2.0 documents and materials are planned to be included in the platform.

3.3.3 DERlab

Full Name: European Distributed Energy Resources Laboratories e.V.

Type: Network (international)

Coordinator: Philipp Strauß (DERlab)

PoC on behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Leonard Ramos (DERlab), Greta Meshi (DERlab), Thomas Strasser (AIT)

PoC on behalf of DERlab: Mohammed Alsaadi (DERlab), Roland Bründlinger (AIT), Graeme Burt (UST)

²³<https://www.mi-ic1smartgrids.net/>

²⁴<https://www.mi-sgiaplatform.net/>

Description: *DERlab*²⁵ is an association of leading laboratories and research institutes in the field of DER equipment and systems. The association develops joint requirements and quality criteria for the connection and operation of DER and strongly supports the consistent development of DER technologies. DERlab offers testing and consulting services for DG to support the transition towards more decentralised power systems.

Collaboration activities: Representatives of both the DERlab Office and the DERlab member network, which consists of over 30 research centres in Europe and the US are involved in the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. DERlab provides possibilities for the project to reach out to these stakeholders and other networks. Through DERlab promotion channels, events, and in the *Database of DER and Smart Grid Research Infrastructure*²⁶, DERlab ensures consistent project visibility to the member network through a permanent communication and dissemination exercise.

3.3.4 IEEE PES Teaching Task Force

Full Name: IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods of Modern Power and Energy Systems

Type: International Network

Coordinator: Panos Kotsampopoulos, Nikos Hatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Panos Kotsampopoulos, Nikos Hatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA), and others

PoC on behalf of IEEE PES Task Force: Panos Kotsampopoulos, Nikos Hatziargyriou (ICCS-NTUA)

Description: *IEEE PES Task Force on innovative teaching methods for modern power and energy systems*²⁷ successfully kicked off during the virtual IEEE PES General Meeting 2020. The Task Force operates in the framework of the University Education Activities Subcommittee of the IEEE PES Power and Energy Education Committee (PEEC) and will investigate, create, and promote the use of innovative teaching methods and materials in modern power and energy systems. Blended learning, innovative laboratory exercises, and e-learning tools will be in particular focus, complemented with interdisciplinary and efficient teaching methods based on engineering education research. Moreover, the Task Force will serve as a forum for sharing and disseminating educational content, tools, and best practices, while exploring cooperation with other PES committees.

In more detail, the Task Force addresses:

- New trends in laboratory education for modern power and energy systems: remote/virtual labs, hardware-in-the-loop simulation, and augmented/virtual reality.
- Transforming the power and energy classroom: blended learning and e-learning tools (e.g. interactive notebooks, animations, Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), etc.)
- Advanced teaching methods for power and energy systems: problem-based learning,

²⁵<http://der-lab.net/>

²⁶<https://infrastructure.der-lab.net/>

²⁷<https://smartgrid.ieee.org/newsletters/october-2020/the-ieee-pes-task-force-on-innovative-teaching-methods-for-modern-power-and-energy-systems>

active learning, interdisciplinary approaches, while addressing different skill levels. Moreover, metrics to evaluate the educational outcomes will be addressed.

- Identification of gaps between the current skill/competence needs of the industry and the output of universities.

Collaboration Activities: Considering the scope of the network and the focus of ERIGrid 2.0 Networking Activities (NA)3 Work Package (WP) on education and training of professionals, researchers and students, there is a lot of collaboration potential.

3.3.5 IEEE WG P2004

Full Name: IEEE WG P2004 - Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation Based Testing of Electric Power Apparatus and Controls

Type: International Network

Coordinator: Michael Steurer (FSU)^{†28}, Georg Lauss (AIT)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Georg Lauss (AIT), Panos Kotsampopoulos (ICCS-NTUA), Antonello Monti (RWTH), Thomas Strasser (AIT), and others

PoC on behalf of IEEE WG P2004: Michael Steurer (FSU), Georg Lauss (AIT)

Description: *IEEE WG P2004*²⁹ is a recommended practice that provides established practices for the use of HIL simulation-based testing of electric power apparatus and controls. It is intended to be generically applicable in conjunction with any specific testing standard (if applicable).

WG P2004 intends to remain agnostic to the specific real-time simulation and power amplifier technologies but focuses on the structures, models, and procedures specific to conducting HIL based testing. P2004 will:

- Establish practices for Robot Operating System (ROS) model development,
- Discuss HIL specific documentation, verification and validation,
- Provide guidance on requirements for power amplifiers, Real-Time Simulation (RTS), and HIL, and interface algorithms for classes of HIL testing needs.

Collaboration Activities: ERIGrid 2.0 focuses and promotes advanced laboratory validation methods for smart grid applications, like HIL simulation-based testing. So, various HIL related developments are planned in the project, thus efforts will be made to integrate the most relevant in the IEEE P2004 document.

3.3.6 IEEE PES Energy Internet Coordinating Committee (EICC) Task Force

Full Name: IEEE PES EICC Task Force on Cloud-Based Control and Co-Simulation of Multi-Party Resources in Energy Internet

Type: International Network

²⁸ <https://www.caps.fsu.edu/news/fsu-foundation-fund-in-memory-of-dr-mischa-steurer/>

²⁹ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2004/11300/>

Coordinator: Xu Yan (Nanyang Technological University, Singapore) and Graeme Burt (UoS, UK)

PoC on Behalf of ERIGrid 2.0: Graeme Burt (UoS)

PoC on behalf of IEEE PES Task Force: Graeme Burt (UoS)

Description: *IEEE PES Task Force on Cloud-Based Control and Co-Simulation of Multi-Party Resources in Energy Internet*³⁰ operates within the framework of Energy Internet Coordinating Committee of the IEEE PES.

In the “Energy Internet” paradigm, DERs can be controlled by different actors via cloud services to achieve various functions. The control architectures, functions, algorithms and validation tools to enable this vision require further investigation. In particular, attention is deserved in the real-world scalability of such solutions, their rigorous validation, and issues arising from their reliance on communications. This Task Force will facilitate the research and development of cloud-based control frameworks and co-simulation platforms for DERs owned by multiple parties in the Energy Internet. The goals of the Task Force are summarised below:

- Identify the emerging challenges of multi-party cloud-based control for DERs, i.e., challenges in their validation, current limitations and potential scalability.
- Design control structures and operational algorithms which achieve frequency/voltage regulation, economic dispatch/operation, health management, etc.
- Establish geographically distributed co-simulation platforms with data exchange via Internet and cloud service to support evaluation and validation of control solutions.

Collaboration Activities: As part of the collaboration between IEEE PES and ERIGrid 2.0, a panel session entitled “*Data-Driven Approaches for Multi-Party Resources Management in Energy Internet Paradigm*” was organised and co-chaired by ERIGrid 2.0 representative Prof. Graeme Burt (UoS) at the *IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting 2023*, held in Orlando (USA) on 16-20 July 2023. The intended audiences included academic researchers and industrial engineers working on the development and validation of decentralised and distributed control of distributed energy resources and multi-party resources management in power systems within the frame of the energy internet.

³⁰<https://cmte.ieee.org/pes-eicc/cloud-based-control-and-co-simulation-of-multi-party-resources-in-energy-internet/>

4 Conclusions

ERIGrid 2.0 forged numerous collaborations, which have been further developed and reinforced during the reporting period spanning from October 1, 2022, to March 31, 2024. This expansive network of partners encompasses thirteen European projects, three national projects, three European initiatives, two national initiatives, and six international initiatives.

With members of the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium active in many other relevant initiatives, the project ensures various points of connection with the smart energy domain. Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 research topics encompass smart energy systems research and development, ensuring a high-quality and cohesive approach undertaken with other initiatives. These topics include:

- Validation and testing needs and possibilities (technology development),
- Advanced power and energy systems technology development and innovation (technology development),
- Multi-domain and cyber-physical based system validation and testing (system validation),
- Integrating pan-European smart energy systems RI (RI Integration),
- Structuring the European smart grid, smart energy systems, energy communities and renewables research area (smart energy research),
- RTS, HIL testing, and co-simulation,
- Multi-lab testing, coupling, and automation (multi-lab testing), and
- Assisting the new generation of educated power and energy systems researchers and engineers, including novel training and educational methodologies (education).

The spectrum of collaboration on these topics is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of topics of collaborations.

Name / Topic	Technology Development	System Validation	RI Integration	Smart Energy Research	RTS, HIL, Co-Simulation	Multi-lab	Education
European Projects							
RISEnergy		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
RICH Europe			✓				✓
int:net	✓	✓	✓			✓	
StoRIES			✓	✓		✓	✓
PANTERA				✓			✓
eNeuron	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓
HYPERRIDE	✓	✓		✓			
SINERGY		✓					✓
RE-EMPOWERED	✓	✓		✓	✓		
JPP Smart Energy Systems		✓					✓

Name / Topic	Technology Development	System Validation	RI Integration	Smart Energy Research	RTS, HiL, Co-Simulation	Multi-lab	Education
European Projects							
ELECTRA	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
EDDIE							✓
RESiii8	✓	✓					
National Projects							
PowerTeams	✓	✓			✓		
NFDI4Energy			✓	✓	✓		✓
APEX							✓
European Initiatives							
EERA JP Smart Grids			✓	✓			
BRIDGE Energy Communities Task Force		✓					
ETIP SNET			✓	✓			
National Initiatives							
Smart Otaniemi			✓				
ENET-RTLlab			✓		✓		
International Initiatives							
IEA ISGAN/SIRFN		✓	✓		✓	✓	
Mission Innovation IC#1 Smart Grids							✓
DERlab	✓	✓		✓			✓
IEEE PES Teaching Task Force							✓
IEEE WG P2004					✓		
IEEE PES EICC Task Force		✓			✓		✓

To wrap up, by actively participating in numerous pertinent initiatives, the consortium members of ERIGrid 2.0 have developed cohesive integration of their research and dissemination endeavours, along with the acquisition of excellent feedback on their research. A wide range of topics have been covered within the different networking and collaboration activities with different initiatives, networks and projects and enriched the knowledge built throughout the project execution.

References

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Consortium

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